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Research Article

**COMPARISON OF THE EFFECTIVENESS MORPHINE AND
MgSo4 PLUS MPORPHINE FOR THE MANAGEMENT OF
PAIN AFTER THE BYPASS SURGERY OF CORONARY
ARTERY**¹Dr Saim Ali Cheema, ²Shameen Ashfaq, ³Dr Muhammad Afzaal¹Rawalpindi Medical College Holy Family Hospital² Allied / DHQ Hospital Faisalabad³ Lahore General Hospital, Lahore**Article Received:** January 2020 **Accepted:** February 2020 **Published:** March 2020**Abstract:**

Objective: The aim of this study is to provide a comparison of efficacy of Morphine and MgSo4 plus Morphine in the management of pain after coronary artery bypass surgery (CABG).

Methodology: This research work was carried out in Holy Family Hospital Rawalpindi. The duration of this study was from December 2018 to July 2019. SPSS V. 23.1 was in use for the analysis of the collected information. Average and standard deviations were in use for the presentation of the numerical information as visual analog scale score and Age of the patients. In the same manner, calculations of sex and status of American society of anesthesia carried out in frequencies. T-test carried out to know the importance of the visual analog scale scores. P value of less than 0.05 was the significant one.

Results: A sum of total 150 patients were the part of this research work. visual analog scale score was the outcome of this research work. We observed in the research that in M group, the average visual analog scale score after 4, 12 and 24 hours of surgery were 5.24 ± 1.61 , 5.8 ± 2.27 and 5.44 ± 2.27 correspondingly. In the MM group, the average visual analog scale score after 4, 12 and 24 hours of surgery were 4.36 ± 2.58 , 3.48 ± 2.1 and 4.12 ± 1.05 correspondingly. The findings showed that there was an important disparity in the visual analog scale scores among both groups, the group M was present with high visual analog scale score in comparison with the visual analog scale scores of group MM.

Conclusion: The effectiveness of the Morphine plus MgSo4 was much better in comparison to the Morphine for the management of pain after the coronary artery bypass surgery.

Keywords: Coronary Artery Bypass Surgery, Effectiveness, Morphine, Analgesia, Visual Analog Scale, MgSo4.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Saim Ali Cheema,**

Rawalpindi Medical College Holy Family Hospital

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Pain is very uncommon feeling of emotion and senses because of the damage of tissues [1]. It is integral part of the life of human and it has variety from low to highly intense state. There are many procedures to relieve the intensity of pains. Among various kinds of pain, pain after the surgical intervention is very irritating for the patients [2]. There is always a condition of fear among patients because of fear after the surgical intervention. It is very vital to relieve the complaints of patients about pain [3]. Sometimes, the not controllable pain is the outcome of the low amount of the analgesia delivered by the professionals [4]. Some of the factors which restrict professionals to manage appropriate analgesia are the drug addiction, intolerance to the drug or the side effects [5]. These factors are also the impediments in the prescription of the analgesics [6]. The relief among inadequate pain among young patients is a serious challenge.

James Moore in 1984 utilized opium for the very 1st time in the patients after surgery as pain reliever [7]. He also provides a justification that usage of opium after surgical intervention is a good analgesia for sleep and good control over irritation [8]. For the management of the pain, there is a variety of the drugs are available now [9] under WASA (World Federation of Societies of Anesthetist) [10]. It is an observation that severity of the pain and impact of opioids are different from person to person, so it is necessary to evaluate the severity of pain and history of drug addiction before the application of any drug [11, 12].

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

The ethical committee of the hospital gave the approval to conduct this research work. Non-probability sampling technique used to select 150 patients. All the patients were from both genders belonged to American society of anesthesia-PS 3 and 4 and they were undergoing surgical intervention for coronary artery bypass surgery. We explained the whole procedure of the study to the patients and obtained their consent. We allocated all the patients randomly to Morphine group and Morphine plus Mgso4 group with the method of lottery. The patients who were suffering from some other serious complication or under the medication were not the part of this research work. We carried

out the complete check-ups and complete investigation before anesthesia for all the patients of the research work.

We gave the ranitidine 150 mg and midazolam as 0.05 mg/kg to all the patients before one of surgical intervention. We also noted the BP, HR and saturation of O₂ before entering in OT. Then the anesthetic solution provided to patients intravenously. Visual Analog Scale scoring carried out for the measurement of the efficacy in both groups. For administration of anesthesia 50% air, 50% O₂, Morphine from 0.10 to 0.2 mg/kg/h, propofol 50 µg/kg/min and atracurium 0.5 mg/kg/h as muscle relaxant were in use in the Group-M, but we provided 4-gram Magnesium Sulphate according to the protocol to the patients of Group-MM. After one hour of surgery, we measured the Visual Analog Scale scores. Visual Analog Scale scoring started after four hours of surgery up to 24 hours after the surgery. If the score on Visual Analog Scale was greater than 3, we gave the analgesic drugs to the patients. SPSS V.23 was in use for the statistical analysis of the collected information. Averages and number were in use for the presentation of the quantitative variables as scores on Visual Analog Scale and age of the patients.

RESULTS:

A sum of 150 patients were the part of this research work. The distribution of the sex displayed that there were 98 (65.3%) male and 52 (34.7%) female patients correspondingly. The average age of the subjects was 60.28 ± 6.54 years. It was the observation that out of patients, 86 (57.3%) patients belong to American society of Anesthesia-3 and 64 (42.7%) patients belong to American society of Anesthesia -4 (Table-1). The division of these patients carried out into 2 groups, 75 in each group i.e. Group-M and Group-MM. The average age of the patients in the Group-M was 59.63 ± 8.34 whereas average age of the patients in the Group-MM was 60.94 ± 3.97 . The distribution of the gender displayed that in Group-M, there were 48 (64%) and 27 (36%) males and females correspondingly whereas in Group-MM, there were 50 (66.7%) and 25 (33.3%) males and female patients correspondingly.

Table-I: Demographic Variables (n=150)

Characteristics		Frequency / Mean	Percentage (%), SD	Test of Sig.
Gender	Male	98	65.3	t=-0.83
	Female	52	34.7	p=0.408
	Total	150	100	
Stratified Age	37-55years	40	26.7	t=2.276
	56-73 years	110	73.3	p=0.024
	Total	150	100	
Stratified BMI	22-28	216	56	t=-0.698
	29-36	170	44	p=0.486
	Total	150	100	
American society of Anesthesia	ASA 3	86	57.3	t=-1.092
	ASA 4	64	42.7	p=0.277
	Total	150	100	
Descriptive Statistics	Age	60.28	6.54	

The visual analog scale score was the main outcome of this research work. This was observation in Group-M that the average visual analog scale score after 4, 12 and 24 hours of surgery was 5.24 ± 1.61 , 5.8 ± 2.27 and 5.44 ± 2.27 correspondingly and in Group-MM, the average visual analog scale score after 4, 12 and 24 hours of surgery was 4.36 ± 2.58 , 3.48 ± 2.1 and 4.12 ± 1.05 correspondingly. We noted that Group-M was available with high visual analog scale score in comparison to the Group-MM. When stratification of the patients carried out into different groups of age, we note different age groups, we noted that most of the patients (73.3%) were present with age 56-76 years whereas only 26.7% patients were present with age 37-55 years (Table-1).

We observed that the average visual analog scale score for the Group-M i.e. 5.49 ± 2.06 was much different as compared to the average visual analog scale score for Group-MM i.e. 3.98 ± 2.02 (Table-2).

Table-II: Visual Analog Scale Score In Both Groups After Treatment

Groups	Time	(Visual Analog Scale Score)	Test of Sig.
		Mean $\pm$ SD	
Group (M)	After 4 hrs of Coronary Artery Bypass Surgery	5.24 ± 1.61	t=4.516
	After 12 hrs of Coronary Artery Bypass Surgery	5.8 ± 2.27	p=0.00
	After 24 hrs of Coronary Artery Bypass Surgery	5.44 ± 2.27	
Group (MM)	After 4 hrs of Coronary Artery Bypass Surgery	4.36 ± 2.58	
	After 12 hrs of Coronary Artery Bypass Surgery	3.48 ± 2.1	
	After 24 hrs of Coronary Artery Bypass Surgery	4.12 ± 1.05	

DISCUSSION:

Cardiac operations are very serious issue in human life and it is the serious challenge for the professionals to control the extreme pain after surgical intervention. Some pain after surgical experience is the very adverse experience in the life of the person [13]. There are many research work on the relive of the pain after the surgical intervention. PE Ozcan, an anesthetist from Turkey in his research work described the part of the MgSO₄ in the management of the pain after surgery [14]. The

results of this research work are comparable with the finding of that research conducted in Turkey. Ferasatkish R in the year of 2008 carried out a research work on the effectiveness of the MgSO₄ for control of pain after coronary artery bypass surgery. He provided a comparison of MgSO₄ plus placebo. Arikan M [16] carried out a research on MgSO₄ and ketamine on the control after surgery and the consumption of Morphine. He concluded that Ketamine is more effective than MgSO₄. Results of current study are similar with that findings.

Nadri S [17] in his study discovered that the group of MgSO₄ has very less visual analog scale scores 0.91 in comparison with the group of controls 1.3. This finding is also comparable with our results. The role of MgSO₄ for relief of pain is not obvious yet [18]. With a dose of very low quantity, it has the ability to suppress the threshold of the pain [19, 20]. In his research work, Lakdizaji S [21] stated that Morphine infusion after the cardiac surgery promotes the relief of pain with very less side effects that it enhances the consumption of the Morphine. In one research work, Guler observed that continuous infusion of Morphine can be very helpful for the ideal administration of the pain. It has the ability to control the pain and results in good consequence of the surgical intervention. Mota FA and Dal D reported the same results.

CONCLUSION:

This research work showed that Morphine plus MgSo₄ is present with high effectiveness in comparison to the only Morphine when utilized as analgesic agent measuring the visual analog scale scores after each 4 hours up to 24 hours after coronary artery bypass surgery.

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